

AUTHORITY

Title	Commonwealth Universities Yearbook
Subtitle	A Directory to the Universities of the commonwealth and the Handbook of their association
Publisher	Association of Commonwealth Universities
First Edition	1913
Latest Publication in print form	82 nd ed. 2008
Language	English
Editor	Paul Turner and other
Volumes	2
CD-ROM	2009
Place of Publication	London

INTRODUCTION

The Association of Commonwealth Universities is an international organisation dedicated to building a better world through higher education.

International collaboration is central to this ambition: by bringing universities together from around the world – and crucially the people who study and work within them – the ACU helps to advance knowledge, promote understanding, broaden minds, and improve lives.

The ACU champions higher education as a cornerstone of stronger societies, supporting its members, partners, and stakeholders as they adapt to a changing world.

The ACU has over 500 member universities in 50 countries across the commonwealth. 66% of our members are in low and middle income countries, and 5% are in small states.

Our network covers over 10 million students and more than 1 million academic and professional staff.

HISTORY

In 1912, on the initiative of the University of London, representatives of 53 universities assembled in London, UK, to hold a Congress of Universities of the Empire. The office of the Universities Bureau of the British Empire was accordingly opened in London in 1913

The ACU is the world's first and oldest international university network, established in 1913 to provide a forum for universities to share information, knowledge and ideas.

Title of the yearbook varies like this:-

1914-47: The Yearbook of the Universities of the Empire.

1948-57: The Yearbook of the universities of the Commonwealth.

1958 till date- Commonwealth Universities Yearbook

SCOPE

- To champion the power of higher education to improve lives
- To support the long-term vitality of universities
- To engage and connect universities across borders, and promote collaboration among them
- To deliver educational opportunities that make a positive and lasting difference
- To uphold the ACU's reputation for excellence and demonstrate its impact
- To build a better world through higher education.
- A world in which higher education transcends borders, strengthens societies, fosters innovation, and lifts the lives of people throughout the Commonwealth and beyond.

ARRANGEMENT

All the entries are arranged alphabetically by the name of country, states and universities. Universities are arranged alphabetically with an introduction.

Volume 1

- Abbreviations to universities, degrees, honors and fellowships

Volume 2

- Appendices
- Index to institutions
- Index to subjects of study
- Index to research interests
- Index to personal names

TREATMENT

Country Profile:

- Map of the country
- Table of subjects to study
- Introduction of the country

University Profiles:

Facts and figures cover:

- History and location
- Faculties/schools with phone/fax numbers, email addresses
- Library holdings
- Academic year: term/semester dates
- Statistics: staff/student figures
- Higher degrees and research interests
- Recurrent income levels

Entries include:

- Dean and secretaries of faculties/schools
- Head/Directors of departments, colleges
- Alphabetical listing by department
- Contacts of officers for queries
- Constituent college information

FORMAT

Available in print, online and CD-ROM

CD-ROM

- Since 2009, a searchable CD-ROM is circulated annually to the members.

Online Version- <http://www.acu.ac.uk>

- Available online at under CUDOS (Commonwealth Universities Database Online Service), only for association of Commonwealth Universities members.

Special Features

- Special notes to the users also provided.
- We strive to excel in all we do, and continuously reflect on our work to find new ways forward
- We believe that cooperation and sharing ideas makes us stronger.

Conclusion

Compiled for academics, resources managers, students and other seeking accurate and reliable data at a global level, the Commonwealth Universities Yearbook is a key resource on every aspect of higher education , senior staff, general faculties, degree program and research. In total, 50 countries are covered in Africa, Asia, Australia, Canada and Europe.

It retains the long-standing reputation for keeping the academic world up to date with the growth and changes taking place in higher education.

**DEPARTMENT OF LIBRARY AND INFORMATION SCIENCE
PANJAB UNIVERSITY, CHANDIGARH**

**ASSIGNMENT
ON
COMMONWEALTH UNIVERSITIES YEARBOOK**

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